

MODIFICATIONS OF IDEAS OF HUMANIZATION OF PEDAGOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13926222>

Abstract. *One of the initial principles of work is considered to be a particularly important means of education - the teacher himself, for he is not just a bearer of knowledge; he invites students to use themselves, their knowledge, experience, their views with which they may not agree; offers students his willingness to provide the means for advancement and knowledge and to help students find these means themselves.*

The main tasks of reforming the system of higher education are reduced to solving the problem of both substantive and organizational-managerial nature, developing a balanced state policy, its orientation towards the ideals and interests of new Uzbekistan. The problem of long-term development of education cannot be solved only through reforms of an organizational-managerial and substantive nature. The question of the need to change the paradigm of education is becoming more and more persistent.

Keywords: *humanization of education, competence, formation, upbringing, education, interactive, methods, education and training pedagogy.*

A significant role in refraction of the growing negative trends in the spiritual sphere of society in our country is given to the pedagogical principle of a way out of this situation proclaimed in the early 90s of the 20th century - the principle of humanization of education. The point is that it is necessary to humanize the activities of professionals. To do this, it is necessary:

firstly, to reconsider the meaning of the concept of "fundamentalization of education", putting a new meaning into it and including it in the basic knowledge of the science of man and society. In Uzbekistan, this is far from a simple problem;

secondly, to form systemic thinking, a single vision of the world without dividing into "physicists" and "lyricists", this will require a reciprocal movement and rapprochement of the parties [2].

Usually, when speaking about the humanitarization of engineering education, they mean only an increase in the share of humanities in the university curriculum. At the same time, students are offered various art history and other humanities disciplines, which are rarely directly related to the future activities of an engineer. But this is the so-called "external humanitarization". Among the scientific and technical intelligentsia, a technocratic style of thinking prevails, which students "absorb" from the very beginning of their studies at the university. Therefore, they treat the study of humanities as something secondary, sometimes displaying outright nihilism [2].

The essence of the humanitarization of education lies primarily in the formation of a culture of thinking, creative abilities of the student based on a deep understanding of the history of culture and civilization, the entire cultural heritage. The university is called upon to prepare a specialist capable of constant self-development, self-improvement, and the richer his nature is, the brighter it will manifest itself in professional activity. If this task is not solved, then, as the Russian philosopher G.P. Fedotov wrote in 1938, "...there is a prospect of an industrial, powerful, but

soulless and spiritual Russia... Naked soulless power is the most consistent expression of Cain's, God-cursed civilization." [3].

The basis of humanization is new target settings that make the human personality a priority, the formation of its creative potential, a humane worldview, which is a benefit both for society and for the person himself. They are based on a change in attitude towards the student, an approach to him as an individual with his own interests, abilities and creative opportunities, which requires the creation of special conditions in the educational process, the development of new methodological systems of training.

The main guiding ideas of the humanization process include: a) orientation of training towards personal development and priority of its developmental function; b) orientation of training towards the final result, correlated with the learning objectives; c) level differentiation of educational requirements, based on the allocation of the level of compulsory training and the level above it; d) ensuring continuity in student's movement along these levels; d) shifting the emphasis from increasing the volume of information intended for assimilation by students to the formation of skills to use information; e) orientation of training towards independent educational activity of schoolchildren; g) humanitarization of education; h) creation of a positive emotional background during training; i) formation of a value attitude towards the subject, personal motives and needs for its study[5].

Changes in the system of educational content are associated with changes in the system of its goals. Didactics of the 20th century understands educational goals as a planned image of the result of the educational process, considers new categories of goals and their hierarchy, methods of complex goal setting, their content and formulation for different levels of assimilation, reflecting the personal aspect. The source of such goal setting is the awareness of the discrepancy between education and the needs, demands, abilities, and capabilities of the student; this makes goal setting the most important parameter in the model of the educational process, which its entire structure depends on. In the context of humanization of education, the main idea of building a classification (taxonomy) of goals is the holistic formation of the student's personality and the idea of a differentiated approach to learning.

According to V.P. Bepalko, the process of learning and development of a student can be represented as a process of ascent from a low to a higher level of assimilation of knowledge by students. This process can actually end at any level. The level of assimilation is distinguished from the level of learning and the level of presentation (material presented at a high level can actually be assimilated by a student at the lowest level) [1].

These and other ideas of the concept of humanization of education were first reflected in the draft National Curriculum "State Standard of Basic General Education" in 2022. It describes the functions of the standard, defines the mandatory minimum content of basic educational programs, the maximum volume of students' academic workload, sets out the requirements for the level of training, etc. The requirements of this standard (currently called the first-generation standard) are that the study of disciplines defined by the curriculum should be aimed at achieving the following goals:

a) mastering subject knowledge sufficient for studying related disciplines at the modern level; b) intellectual development by means of the academic discipline, necessary for training and future professional activity; c) development of ideas about the discipline as part of universal culture, its significance in the history of civilization and modern society; d) formation of ideas

about the discipline as a form of description and method of cognition of reality, its ideas and methods, their features and differences from the methods of other sciences. It is noted that all goals are considered as equally significant for the formation of personality in the process of mastering the discipline. Currently, goals are also presented in the language of key competencies.

Humanization of modern education is a global phenomenon, which is explained by three reasons: humanization is called upon, firstly, to ensure a civilized and reasonable use of scientific and technical potential, environmental resources and social aspects, secondly, to introduce society to the cultural values of its people, and thirdly, to ensure an order for new knowledge and science.

Humanization of education in a philosophical context presupposes a certain focus on understanding spirituality, and an ethical and aesthetic attitude to the surrounding world. Modern socio-philosophical thought finds that the cultural potential of humanity is the basis that determines the specifics of human existence, the nature of social evolution [6].

At present, the concept of "humanization of education" is at the stage of formation and comprehension, so the definition is ambiguous.

Thus, T.A. Ivanova believes that the humanitarization of education is a multifaceted and complex phenomenon aimed at developing and forming universal human values, mastering humanitarian knowledge and humanitarian culture. Humanitarization of education, according to T.N. Mirakova, is the improvement of culture by expanding the general cultural component of education, which involves both an increase in the number of humanitarian disciplines in the curriculum and the acquisition of new humanitarian knowledge. I.M. Oreshnikov believes that the humanitarization of education in a broad sense includes all humanization, is based on it, but the main thing here is the formation of a humanitarian culture of an individual, strengthening the humanitarian training of people, saturating natural and special disciplines with cultural, human, and ideological issues. The principle of humanitarization of education means, firstly, identifying the humanitarian potential of disciplines, allowing us to talk about them as part of human culture. Secondly, it is reflected in the content of education, which forms a holistic idea of the scientific picture of the world. Thirdly, the principle is implemented in teaching methods that allow the formation of experience in mental, search, creative, labor and other activities of students, the experience of their emotional-value relationships, etc.

The task of humanitarian education is to develop the ability to think, strengthen ethical principles, enrich the spiritual sphere of the individual. The decisive quality of the education of the individual is the ability to think. This ability is manifested by the degree of use of personal experience in the process of thinking and only in this way can it be formed. The development of thinking should primarily be served by the humanitarian cycle of education of a student at university. An integral system of humanitarian education should conditionally include knowledge divided into three groups (spheres): knowledge of the individual about himself and his kind; knowledge of the social sphere in which he is included; knowledge of the external world (living and inanimate nature), in which societies of individuals are located. Each of these spheres requires a special set of subjects and a special methodology. Pedagogical theory and practice are in constant search of new substantive foundations of humanitarian and general cultural education, new technologies of teaching, training and retraining of specialists, advanced training.

The main directions of the humanitarization of education: 1) restoration of the humanitarian principles of science (its history, its creators, philosophical principles, spiritual purpose); 2) introduction of methods and forms inherent in the humanities into teaching methodology;

3) approximation to the social existence of a person (application of elements of specialized knowledge in everyday life, personal significance of their study, integration with the humanities);

4) providing students with opportunities to realize their individual abilities through a variety of types of educational activities for studying the discipline.

Thus, by the humanitarization of education we mean the transfer of education to a humanitarian basis, i.e.:

a) approximation of the study of the discipline to a person, his interests, needs and abilities;

b) creation of holistic knowledge about the world (through interdisciplinary connections, practical focus, etc.);

c) organization of various types of activities for self-expression and self-affirmation, support and stimulation of independence.

The main ideas of developmental learning were formulated by L.S. Vygotsky: "...development processes do not coincide with learning processes, the former follow the latter, creating zones of proximal development...; ...although learning is directly connected with child development, nevertheless, they never proceed evenly and in parallel with each other, ... learning is not development, but, if properly organized, it leads to child mental development, brings to life a number of such processes that would become impossible without learning". From the standpoint of developmental learning, L.S. Vygotsky identified the following types of learning activity: reproductive, reconstructive (reproduction of methods of obtaining facts), variable (reproduction of mental operations). The founders of the theory of developmental learning noted that one of the tasks of constructing such learning is to change the content of curricula so that the stock of knowledge ceases to be something empirical: students should think more than remember, prepare for long-term and increasingly demanding learning activities with age. According to L.S. Vygotsky, the mental development of children and adolescents is based on language and action, "embedded" in a particular culture. Therefore, the goal of modern general education – the holistic development of student's personality – can be realized only with adequate content, including such a component as methods of educational activity for achieving this development.

These provisions were developed by scientists of his psychological school (A.N. Leontiev, L.V. Zankov, D.B. Elkonin, V.V. Davydov, V.V. Repkin, etc.), and are presented in the form of experimentally tested methodological systems of primary education. Other ideas come from the theory of the stage-by-stage formation of mental actions by P.Ya. Galperin, in which an important role is given to the orienting basis of activity; from the concept of developmental learning by I.S. Yakimanskaya, which substantiates the need for the purposeful formation of methods of educational activity in students; from the concept of personality-oriented learning, which puts the originality of the child at the forefront (A.G. Asmolov, E.D. Bozhovich, E.V. Bondarevskaya, V.V. Serikov, etc.) [5].

Activity in psychology is the process of human activity associated with its interaction with the surrounding reality and focus on a certain subject of activity (creation of the product of activity, acquisition of knowledge, self-development), which can be carried out in different forms (differing in subject content) and at different levels. In some types of activity, actions are internal (separated from practical actions), in others - external (the product of which is expressed in a certain object). But in any human activity, theoretical actions are involved, and the more complex the practice, the more significant the role of preliminary theoretical actions.

Theoretical actions, in turn, can take place both in an internal and external form (making it possible to make them visible and thereby helping to master them). External and internal activities have a common structure, so there are constant interactions and transitions between them. Educational activity is the activity of mastering the accumulated knowledge of society about the subject of study and general methods of solving problems associated with it; without it, it is impossible to master other types of human activity - industrial work, artistic creativity, sports, etc. This is a special form of student activity aimed at changing himself as a subject of learning, the main type of activity of schoolchildren, forming not only knowledge, skills and abilities, but also attitudes, volitional and emotional qualities, i.e. the personality as a whole [7].

Based on the analysis of the primary education system, D.B. Elkonin in 1961 put forward a hypothesis about educational activity and its structure, the need to organize a special type of student activity and master the methods of this activity. In the theory of educational activity, it is shown that the mastery of the content of training occurs not by transmitting some information to him, but in the process of his own active activity.

This position is the psychological basis of the concept of an activity-based approach to learning, which, according to the characteristics of N.F. Talyzina, raised questions about the relationship between knowledge, skills and abilities of students and their development in educational activity in a new way. Knowledge is acquired only in activity, behind student's skills and abilities there is always an action with certain characteristics (perception, awareness, memorization, reproduction, etc.). Formation of educational activity is the management by an adult of the process of formation of the educational activity of students. Under this controlling influence, the child relatively quickly becomes the subject of educational activity, and then, as its formative "levers" weaken, we can talk about its development.

From the standpoint of the general theory of activity, psychologists distinguish between the concepts of "learning activity" and "teaching"; the former is broader than the latter, since it includes both the activity of the teacher and the activity of the learner.

The theory of learning activity shows that the assimilation of the content of training and the development of the student occur in the process of his own active educational and cognitive activity on perception, comprehension, memorization, application, generalization and systematization of information, control and assessment of its assimilation. These processes form a complete cycle of student's educational and cognitive activity.

The main structural component of learning activity is the learning task - a generalized goal of the activity, set (formulated) before students in the form of an educational assignment, by completing which students acquire the relevant knowledge and skills, learn to learn. Setting the learning task is the motivational and orientation link - the first link in learning activity; awareness of the triad "motive - goal - result" is an important prerequisite for learning activity. Its second (central) link is the executive one, i.e. educational actions to solve an educational problem [9].

In studies of the problem of "teaching schoolchildren to learn" the problem of developing general educational skills and abilities of a universal nature, called "the ability to learn", is highlighted, since its presence means in each specific case a rational organization of educational activities: a) organization of educational work; b) work with a book and other sources of information; c) the culture of oral and written speech. In order to achieve such goals, the content of training should include the corresponding educational tasks and methods for solving them -

techniques of educational activity. Teaching methods aimed at organizing, forming and developing the educational activities of schoolchildren should take into account: a) the uniqueness of educational needs, motives, tasks, actions and operations; b) various stages of development throughout school childhood; c) the dynamics of the components of educational activity themselves, their transitions from one to another; d) the relationship of learning with other types of activity of the child; d) the individuality of the forms of educational activity. The achievement of new educational goals could not be achieved only by traditional teaching methods, which did not address the problem of students' cognitive activity, memory dominated over thinking, which resulted in passivity in academic work, mental laziness, and cramming. This type of teaching increasingly did not suit society, so the arsenal of teaching methods began to expand [8]. New socio-economic realities are characterized by such features as orientation towards knowledge, virtualization of the environment and relations between its structures, integration and inter-network interaction, elimination of intermediaries, innovation, dynamism, globalization and the presence of contradictions. One of the requirements for a "good employee" today is defined as follows: if previously strong muscles were required of him, now - strong nerves: psychological stability, readiness for overload and stressful situations, readiness to get out of them. Another requirement is readiness for change, the ability to make choices, effectively use limited resources, compare theoretical solutions with practice, negotiate, quickly find information and use it to solve their problems, etc. From the standpoint of the competency-based approach, the level of education of graduates of educational institutions should be determined by the ability to solve problems of varying complexity based on existing knowledge and experience.

According to the Strategy for Modernization of Education, the implementation of the competency-based approach in education requires solving, in particular, the following tasks:

1) analysis of the relationship between the competency-based and traditional approaches in Uzbek schools;

2) development and clarification of the list of key competencies and recommendations for their development at different levels of school and on different subject materials;

3) interpretation of the existing content of general education in an activity-based form and in a system of coordinates defined by key competencies;

4) interpretation of the key competencies themselves in an activity-based form, which corresponds to the focus on their actual use by students in life;

5) development of technologies based on the competency-based approach. Thus, the traditional system of measures - knowledge, skills, abilities - does not correspond to the new paradigm of education. From the standpoint of the competency-based approach, the main immediate result of education should be key competencies, which should perform three functions:

1) help students learn;

2) allow them to meet employers' demands;

3) help them become more successful in their future lives and not be "a repetition" of traditional measures that disguise old educational problems under a new sign.

Therefore, the competency-based approach requires a reorientation of the dominant educational paradigm from the predominant transmission of knowledge, the formation of skills to the creation of conditions for mastering a set of competencies that mean the potential, the ability

of a graduate to survive and sustain life in the conditions of a modern multifactorial socio-political, market-economic, information and communication-saturated space.

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